

Original Article

Risk Factors of Recurrent Wheeze in First 24 Months of Life

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Abstract:

Background: Recurrent wheezing early in life has been implicated as a factor for adverse respiratory outcomes later in life. Factors that predispose children to recurrent wheezing have not been conclusively defined.

Objectives: To find out the risk factors of recurrent wheeze in children in 1st 2 years of age.

Methodology: It was a case-control study. The children who attended the OPD of the Institute of Child and Mother Health with 3 or more attacks of wheeze in 1st 2 years of life were studied through a structured pretested questionnaire. The questionnaires were filled up through a face to face interview with mothers.

Results: The mean age of children with recurrent wheeze was 11.3 months and that for the controls was 13.8 months. The median age of the first attack of wheeze was 3 months and about one third (31%) required hospitalization signifying severe attack. There were past history of pneumonia in 31% cases and bronchiolitis in 15% cases. Male children were found to suffer more recurrent wheeze than female peers (OR 2.37, 95% CI 1.32-4.26). The chance of recurrent wheeze in children was double if parents were poor rather than not poor (OR 1.91, 95% CI 1.05- 3.48). The children were more likely to suffer from recurrent wheeze if they had atopic conditions; 4 times in case of atopic dermatitis (OR 4.25, 95% CI 1.25-15.77), more than 3 times (OR 3.59, 95% CI 1.04- 13.59) in case of allergic conjunctivitis and 4 times (OR 4.25, 1.72- 10.87) in case of allergic rhinitis. We did not find any significant relationship with breast feeding, time of birth, birth weight, nutritional status, number of family members staying in one room, rented house, maternal asthma, using wood stove and environmental tobacco smoke.

Conclusion: This case control study highlights the risk factors of recurrent wheeze in 1st 2 years of life of children. Recurrent wheeze was more common in male child and poor socio economic condition. Other atopic condition like allergic rhinitis, allergic conjunctivitis and atopic dermatitis were found to be risk factors for recurrent wheeze.

Key words: Risk factors, recurrent wheeze, 1st 2 years of child.

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Introduction

Wheeze is a high pitched whistling sounds arising from chest during expiration. It is the second most common respiratory noise next to cough¹. Respiratory illness in children is a major health hazard, both in the developed and developing countries. Wheezing in children is one of the common manifestations of many respiratory illnesses. Wheezing is a common clinical entity more often seen in infants than older children. The intensity of wheeze may vary with person to person, from time to time, even in the same individual. At

times, it presents with an alarming severity. Child may be agitated, apprehensive and crying. Severe wheezing may interfere with sucking, swallowing, sleep and other day-to-day activities. Manifestation of wheeze results in minimal or gross alteration in the lung function according to the degree of narrowing of airway lumen. Alteration of lung function in children with wheeze may lead to immediate or late sequelae and occasionally leads to multi-system involvement. Wheezing in a child is potentially problematic and at times, hazardous and dangerous. Wheezing is a prolonged musical sound of varying intensity produced by the passage of air through narrowed bronchi, invariably heard during expiration and audible, even without stethoscope. Wheezes are musical sounds, which are classified according to pitch (high and low), complexity (monophonic and polyphonic), duration (long and short) and timing (inspiratory and expiratory; early and late; random and sequential). Musical lung sounds are usually called 'wheezes' when heard at a distance or at the mouth, and 'rhonchi' when heard through the chest wall. Recurrent cough and wheeze in infancy are common problems in general pediatric outpatient clinics and practice^{2,3}. Wheezing in early childhood is a heterogeneous condition. The most common causes of recurrent wheezes are asthma, pneumonia, bronchiolitis, gastro-oesophageal reflux diseases and pulmonary tuberculosis. Other causes of wheeze are foreign body aspiration, tracheomalacia, cystic fibrosis etc. Asthma is certainly an important cause of recurrent wheeze in children. Bronchial hyperresponsiveness (BHR) is a universally recognized phenomenon of asthma⁴. Certain infections (respiratory syncytial virus- RSV, adenovirus, Bordetella pertussis) seem to be capable of inducing airway disease that can cause symptoms for months or even years⁵. Bronchiolitis (mostly due to RSV) is another important cause of wheeze in young children. Recurrent wheezing in young children can also result from exposure to excessive environmental tobacco smoke (ETS). Exposure to ETS especially in antenatal period can cause abnormal airway function from birth and increases the risk of respiratory illness associated with wheezing. Premature birth, even without neonatal respiratory illness, predisposes to cough and wheeze in infancy⁶. It indicates an early allergic sensitization in wheezing infants, suggesting an

altered immune-regulatory T-cell role in immunoglobulin E production⁷. Lower respiratory tract illnesses are frequent in children who are 0 to 2 years of age and have a positive relationship with some risk factors⁸.

Methodology

It was a case control study. Data were collected through a questionnaire from parents having children with recurrent wheeze and the age at or below 24 months of age. Study duration was 6 months from June to December 2003. Study population was children from pediatrics inpatient and outpatient department of the Institute of Child and Mother Health. 100 children were case and 100 children were control. Three or more attacks of wheeze in children within the first 24 months of life were labeled as case (recurrent wheeze). Children in EPI department within the first 24 months of life who did not suffer from any wheeze previously were labeled as control. Data were analyzed in Epi-info program.

Results:

A total of 100 cases and 100 controls were studied, study group included cases and control from 1 month up to 24 months of life. The mean age of wheezing was 11.3 months with the range of 1 - 23 months and that for the control was 13.8 months and range between 1 – 19 months. The median age for first attack of wheeze was 3 months and 31% cases required hospitalization signifying severe attack. Profession of most of the fathers of were labour and that of mothers were housewife. There were past history of pneumonia (fever, cough and respiratory distress) in 31% cases and bronchiolitis (first attack of wheeze) in 15% cases. The socioeconomic background in both cases and controls were shown in table I.

Table II showed 72% male and 28% female in case group, 52% male and 48% female in control group. Odds ratio 2.37, 95% CI 1.32 – 4.26 was statistically significant. The chance of recurrent wheeze in male child was more than two times higher compared to female child.

Table III showed relationship of poor socioeconomic condition with recurrent wheeze. Those with 3000 tk /month or less income were considered poor and those with more than 3001 per month were labeled as not poor. This table showed that chance of recurrent wheeze was almost two times more in poor compared to not poor groups (OR 1.91, 95% CI 1.05-3.48).

Table I*Socio-economic status of both cases and control*

Parameters	Cases	Control
Mean year of schooling in case of fathers	9.95	6.87
Mean year of schooling in case of mothers	4.55	5.16
Profession of fathers		
• Day Labour	32%	26%
• Small traders	20%	21%
• Service	18%	19%
• Other	30%	34%
Profession of mothers		
• Housewife	91%	96%
• Other	9%	4%
Monthly family income		
• Tk 3000/- or less	58%	42%
• Tk 3001-10000/-	39%	54%
• Tk > 10000/-	03%	04%
Housing		
• Rented		
• Owned	59%41%	55%45%

Table IV showed relationship between exclusive breast feeding and recurrent wheeze. The odds ratio for recurrent wheeze was 0.90, 95% CI 0.46-1.77, which means that there was 10% less chance of recurrent wheeze if exclusive breast feeding was practiced though the value was not statistically significant.

Table V & VI showed relationship between time of birth and recurrent wheeze. There was more chance of recurrent wheeze if born in the month of October through March (OR 1.93, 95% CI 0.75-5.02) but it was somewhat protective against recurrent wheeze if baby was born in the month of April through September (OR 0.49, 95% CI 0.18-1.32). However this finding were not statistically significant.

Table VII showed relationship between atopic dermatitis with recurrent wheeze. It was found from the table that children with atopic dermatitis were 4 times more vulnerable to recurrent wheeze compared to non atopic groups (OR 4.25, 95% CI 1.25-15.77).

Table II*Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to sex*

	Group				95% CI		
		Case	Control	Total	OR	Lower	Upper
Sex	Male	72	52	124			
		72.0%	52.0%	62.0%			
	Female	28	48	76	2.37	1.32	4.26
		28.0%	48.0%	38.0%			
Total		100	100	200			
		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%			

Table III*Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to monthly income*

	Group				95% CI		
		Case	Control	Total	OR	Lower	Upper
Income	3000 or less	58	42	100			
		58.0%	42.0%	50.0%			
	3001-5000	29	43	72			
		29.0%	43.0%	36.0%			
	5001-10000	10	11	21	1.91	1.05	3.48
		10.0%	11.0%	10.5%			
	Above10000	3	4	7			
		3.0%	4.0%	3.5%			
Total	100	100	200				
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%				

Table IV*Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to breast feeding pattern*

		Group			OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control	Total		Lower	Upper
Breast feeding	EBF	26	28	54	0.90	0.46	1.77
		26.0%	28.0%	27.0%			
	PBF	5	8	72			
	Mixed feeding	69	64	133			
		69.0%	64.0%	66.5%			
Total	100	100	200				
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%				

Table V*Distribution of recurrent wheeze according to months of child birth*

		Group			OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control	Total		Lower	Upper
Month of birth	Oct	8	8	16	1.93	0.75	5.02
		8.0%	8.0%	8.0%			
	Nov	8	10	18			
		8.0%	10.0%	9.0%			
	Dec	10	14	24			
		10.0%	14.0%	12.0%			
	Jan	11	14	25			
	11.0%	14.0%	12.5%				
	Feb	7	4	11			
		7.0%	4.0%	5.5%			
	Mar	16	9	25			
		16.0%	9.0%	12.5%			
Total	100	100	200				
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%				

Table VI*Distribution of recurrent wheeze according to months of child birth*

		Group			OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control	Total		Lower	Upper
Month of birth	April	7	7	14	0.49	0.18	1.32
		7.0%	7.0%	7.0%			
	May	7	5	12			
		7.0%	5.0%	6.0%			
	June	2	3	5			
		2.0%	3.0%	2.5%			
	July	8	6	14			
	8.0%	6.0%	7.0%				
	Aug	8	15	23			
		8.0%	15.0%	11.5%			
	Sept	8	5	13			
		8.0%	5.0%	6.5%			
Total	100	100	200				
	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%				

Table VIII showed relationship of allergic conjunctivitis with recurrent wheeze. The children with allergic conjunctivitis had almost 4 times more attack of recurrent wheeze compared to non allergic groups (OR 3.59, 95% CI 1.04-13.59).

Table IX showed relationship of allergic rhinitis with recurrent wheeze. There was more than 4 times of higher risk of recurrent wheeze in children with allergic rhinitis than in non allergic rhinitis groups (OR 4.25, 95% CI 1.72- 10.87).

Table X showed relationship between maternal asthma and recurrent wheeze in children. The Odds ratio for recurrent wheeze in children was 1.46, 95% CI 0.61 –3.47 if mother was a patient of asthma. The value was not significant. It means there was

no relationship between maternal asthma and recurrent wheeze in children.

Table XI showed relationship between father's asthma and recurrent wheeze in children. The Odds ratio for recurrent wheeze in children was 1.46, 95% CI 0.61 –3.47 if father was a patient of asthma. The value was not significant. It means there was no relationship of paternal asthma with recurrent wheeze in children.

Table XII showed relationship between wheezy sibs and recurrent wheeze in the children. The Odds ratio for recurrent wheeze if any other sib has had wheeze was 0.98, 95% CI 0.44-2.18. It means there was no relationship between wheezy sibs and recurrent wheeze.

Table VII

Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to presence or absence of atopic dermatitis

		Group		Total	OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control			Lower	Upper
Atopic dermatitis	Yes	15 15.0%	4 4.0%	19 9.5%	4.25	1.25	15.77
	No	85 85.0%	96 96.0%	181 90.5%			
Total		100 100.0%	100 100.0%	200 100.0%			

Table VIII

Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to presence or absence of allergic conjunctivitis

		Group		Total	OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control			Lower	Upper
Allergic conjunctivitis	Yes	13 13.0%	4 4.0%	17 8.5%	3.59	1.04	13.59
	No	87 87.0%	96 96.0%	183 91.5%			
Total		100 100.0%	100 100.0%	200 100.0%			

Table IX

Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to presence or absence of allergic rhinitis

		Group		Total	OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control			Lower	Upper
Allergic rhinitis	Yes	27 27.0%	8 8.0%	35 17.5%	4.25	1.72	10.87
	No	73 73.0%	92 92.0%	165 82.5%			
Total		100 100.0%	100 100.0%	200 100.0%			

Table X
Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to presence or absence of maternal asthma

		Group			OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control	Total		Lower	Upper
Maternal asthma	Yes	14 14.0%	10 10.0%	24 12.0%	1.46	0.61	3.47
	No	86 86.0%	90 90.0%	176 88.0%			
Total		100 100.0%	100 100.0%	200 100.0%			

Table XI
Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to presence or absence of father's asthma

		Group			OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control	Total		Lower	Upper
Father's asthma	Yes	9 9.0%	4 4.0%	13 6.5%	1.46	0.61	3.47
	No	91 91.0%	96 96.0%	187 93.5%			
Total		100 100.0%	100 100.0%	200 100.0%			

Table XII
Distribution of recurrent wheeze among cases and controls according to presence or absence of wheeze in sibs

		Group			OR	95% CI	
		Case	Control	Total		Lower	Upper
Wheeze in sibs	Yes	18 18.0%	21 21.0%	39 19.5%	0.98	0.44	2.18
	No	49 49.0%	56 56.0%	105 52.5%			
	NA	33 33.0%	23 23.0%	56 28.0%			
Total		100 100.0%	100 100.0%	200 100.0%			

Discussion

Factors that predispose infants and young children to wheezing illness have not been conclusively defined. There are different categories of wheezers: transient early wheezers, (occurring before three years of age but not at the age of six months), late-onset wheezers (children who had no wheezing

within the first three years) which was the most common pattern among older children and young adults and persistent wheezers. Those with persistent wheezing had significantly higher levels of IgE than those who had never wheezed⁹. The factors considered in our study were sex; birth weight; gestational age; time of birth; consanguinity

between parents; wheeze in other sibs; breast feeding; parental education; parental asthma; socioeconomic conditions like monthly income, number of family members staying in one room and housing; nutritional status; associated other conditions like allergic rhinitis, atopic eczema and allergic conjunctivitis; and indoor domestic fire source; past history of pneumonia and bronchiolitis. The risk factors for recurrent wheeze which were found significant in this study were past history of pneumonia, bronchiolitis, male sex, poor economic condition, atopic dermatitis, allergic rhinitis and allergic conjunctivitis. This was a questionnaire based case control study. The mean age of cases and control were matched (11.3 months Vs 13.8 months). The number of children in control group was equal in both sexes (male 52% Vs female 48%). The study has a number of limitations. The data were mainly collected by recall method by the mothers and there might be some dearth of authenticity during the process of data collection. Diagnosis of pneumonia and bronchiolitis were made from history emphasizing on the presence of fever, cough, respiratory distress and wheeze. Importance of wheeze was given to consider bronchiolitis¹⁰. There were more cases of male (72%) than female (52%) who suffered from recurrent wheeze. The difference was statistically significant (OR 2.37, 95% CI 1.32-4.26). Male children are always vulnerable to recurrent wheeze and asthma as observed in other studies¹¹. Acute lower respiratory illness (LRI) early in life has been implicated as a factor for adverse respiratory outcomes later in life. Pneumonia and bronchiolitis are important causes of LRI with wheezing^{12,13}. In our study there was history of pneumonia in 31% cases and bronchiolitis in 15% cases as against no cases of such LRI in the control group. Reduced lung function in the early life may predispose infants to LRI with wheezing in the first two years of life¹⁴. We found significant relation with poor economic condition and recurrent wheeze (OR 1.91, 95% CI 1.05-3.48). Similar finding was observed in Bangladesh national asthma prevalence study where asthma was seen in less privileged social class of 'deficit' and 'illiterate' group of people¹⁵. But we did not find any significant relationship of recurrent wheeze with illiteracy of parents. Different atopic conditions were found significantly associated with recurrent wheeze. The OR for atopic dermatitis was 4.25, 95% CI 1.25-

15.77; OR for allergic rhinitis 4.25, 95% CI 1.72-10.87; OR for allergic conjunctivitis 3.59, 95% CI 1.04-13.59. The chance of having recent wheeze (wheeze in last 12 months) was found to be 3 times more when one had recent rhinitis as against normal children (not having rhinitis) (OR 3.68, 95% CI 3.01-4.49). The chance of having recent wheeze was found to be more than 4 times when one had conjunctivitis (OR 4.39, 95% CI 3.42-5.63). Similarly, the chance for recent wheeze was observed to be about double when one had eczema (OR 1.90, 95% CI 1.38-2.61).

Breast feeding has long been believed to be responsible for less occurrence of recurrent wheeze among non-atopic children¹⁶. Our observation partially conforms the results of the study but not statistically significant (OR 0.90, 95% CI 0.46-1.77). Bisgaard H had shown that children who were born in the period of April through September develop wheezing more often than children born in October through March but our study finding (OR 0.96, 95% CI 0.52-1.96) does not suggest this notion¹⁷. There was no particular period when children were born found to be vulnerable to recurrent wheeze in this study. No correlation were observed in case of LBW, preterm delivery, living in rented house, history of parental asthma, nutritional status as measured by z-score, number of family members living in one room, wheezy sibs in the family, use of wood as fuel in the kitchen and environmental tobacco smoking (ETS) by the parents in this study. But study conducted by Kelly et al showed the symptom triad of cough, wheeze and breathlessness was significantly associated with having been born prematurely, rented accommodation, passive smoking, maternal asthma, maternal smoking and wood smoke¹⁸.

Conclusion:

This case control study highlights the risk factors of recurrent wheeze in 1st 2 years of life of children. Recurrent wheeze was more common in male child and poor socio economic condition. Atopic conditions like allergic rhinitis, allergic conjunctivitis and atopic dermatitis are risk factor for recurrent wheeze.

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